

A Preprocessing Pipeline for Histopathological Whole Slide Images

Neel Kanwal, Kjersti Engan, Chunming Rong
Dept. of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science
University of Stavanger
Stavanger, Norway
{neel.kanwal, kjersti.engan, chunming.rong}@uis.no

Abstract

Introduction: Digital pathology (DP) refers to the use of a virtual microscope by digital scanning of tissue slides, producing Whole-slide Images (WSI). WSI are very high-resolution and information-rich. Different laboratories and scanners can have slightly different protocols and colour variations that can be present even within the same lab and scanner. A WSI can contain a variety of artefacts. These artefacts may result from the tissue being cauterized, or from the preparation of the slide. We propose a preprocessing pipeline to cover necessary steps and filters to detect regions of the WSI that should be discarded before further processing with machine learning models.

Methods: WSI are gigapixel images, thus associated with high memory and computational cost. A modular and sequential approach is deemed fit to tackle different challenges in preprocessing WSI; the following steps are proposed:

- 1) *Quality Check:* Assessing WSI with technical metadata parameters such as file format and resolution may help in excluding inappropriate files. For datasets, batch-level outliers can be found based on tissue morphology, contrast and placement (for example HistQC software [1]).
- 2) *Patching:* Patching is necessary before high-resolution processing due to the large size of the WSI. Patching is often performed as grid patching at the highest resolution, but can be defined over multiple resolutions, different sizes, and restricted to be inside manually annotated regions.
- 3) *Patch Exclusion:* Tissue folds, blood, damaged areas, air bubbles and focal blurs are examples of artefacts or areas with no diagnostic relevance, and we wish to detect such patches to omit them from further processing. Examples of techniques to tackle such problems are: i) Conversion to HSV colour space followed by thresholding hue for detecting blood and value for detecting folded tissue in combination with line detection. ii) Laplace and Gaussian filters can detect blur combining divergence and slope of local maxima. iii) convolutional neural networks classifying patches as damaged or blood vs. diagnostically relevant tissue [2].
- 4) *Colour Variation:* Colour augmentation and Colour normalization are common methods for improving the robustness of models against stain variations. Stain normalization based on colour deconvolution results in better structural similarity in quantitative evaluation compared to colour matching methods but might be computationally demanding. Colour augmentation adds a range of values in HSV channels and generalizes the model against different stain variants.
- 5) *Patch Selection:* Relevant patches can be selected from segmented regions, by sub-sampling and for class balancing depending on the task, like diagnosis, prognosis, image retrieval etc. Different tissue types are relevant for cancer staging and grading.

Conclusion: The heterogeneous WSI datasets obtained from different labs exhibit significant variations due to scanner, age of the slide, manual dyeing and other artefacts. We have presented a generalized five-step preprocessing pipeline to cope with all challenges in handling high-resolution histological images. Although, it is hard to establish a single preprocessing pipeline standard for all diseases and subsequent analyses. The formulated method is suitable for preprocessing for various task-based classifiers.

Keywords - Whole Slide Images, Preprocessing, Artefacts, Histology, Image processing, Machine learning, Colour normalization

Figure 1: The proposition of a five-stage pipelines to cater different artefacts in WSI

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